

Online Shopping – Opinion of College Students

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Abstract

Online shopping is also known as E-Shopping and it allows consumer directly to buy goods and services from a seller through internet using websites or mobile applications. Online shopping attitude refers to consumer's psychological state in terms of making purchases on the Internet e-Commerce is a general concept covering any form of business transaction or information exchange executed using Information and Communication Technology (ICT's). E-Commerce takes place between companies and their consumers, or between companies & Government. E-Commerce includes buying and selling of goods and services and doing business over electronic- computer networks. There is huge scope of web-stores in various areas and in almost all the segments. The young population is the biggest attraction of this industry and they may contribute substantially to the growth of online shopping in India. The majority of internet users are youngsters, the majority of goods and services demanded are related to only this segment. This paper aims to analyse the general opinion of college students on online shopping, rank the advantages of online shopping, mentioned by the college students, and identify the problems of online shopping point out by the college students, advantages and its future and conclusion.

Keywords: Online shopping, advantages, limitations, identify the problems.

Introduction

Online shopping is a form of electronic commerce which allows consumers to directly buy goods or services from a seller over the Internet using a web browser. Consumers find a product of interest by visiting the website of the retailer directly or by searching among alternative vendors using a shopping search engine, which displays the same product's availability and pricing at different e-retailers. As of 2016, customers can shop online using a range of different computers and devices, including desktop computers, laptops, tablet computers and smart phones.

An online shop evokes the physical analogy of buying products or services at a regular "bricks-and-mortar" retailer or shopping center; the process is called business-to-consumer (B2C) online shopping. When an online store is set up to enable businesses to buy from another businesses, the process is called business-to-business (B2B)

online shopping. A typical online store enables the customer to browse the firm's range of products and services, view photos or images of the products, along with information about the product specifications, features and prices.

Statement of the Problem

Online purchasing of goods, both expensive and cheap, is prevalent to a much larger extent in recent years due to convenience, speed transactions, saving time, attractive sales promotional offers, etc.. Despite these motivational factors, there are various transactional and non-transactional issues involved such as internet users being uncomfortable while giving their credit card number, personal information, etc. which act as deterrents. Online shopping is new, and it is at a nascent stage, and there are no hard-and-fast rules to live by. Consumers are slow in showing interest in online shopping. However, the future for internet shopping looks bright and promising. Therefore, this study aims to examine the attitude of online shopper.

College students choose to shop online because of the convenience. The college students take part in online shopping determines its success. In this context, it is essential to study the socio-economic satisfaction of college students and through general opinion.

Review of Literature

In this field few studies were conducted in India. The researcher reviewed many researchers conducted in India and abroad to find out the correct area to carry out the research work, which will be fruitful for the professionals and country.

- Total Review – 51
- It is related with.....
- Studies related to Online shopping

Objectives of the Study

- To know the social- economic profile of college students.
- To analyse the general opinion of college students on online shopping.
- To rank the advantages of online shopping, mentioned by the college students.
- To rank the problems of online shopping point out by the college students.

Research Design

A. Source of information

The research based on both primary data and secondary data.

a) Primary data

The primary data collected through a well structure Questionnaire under a guidance of the supervisor.

b) Secondary data

The secondary data was collected from the journals, and website.

B. Sampling Design

The primary data were collected from 130 respondents. By adopting convenience sampling method.

C. Statistical Tools

- Percentage Analysis
- Garrett Ranking

Limitation of the Study

- The researcher has conducted research in college students only.
- The period of the study has been restricted to one year(2017-18).
- There is a chance of biased information from the online shopping the research has no previous experience.

Analysis & Interpretation

Online Portals Preferred

S. No	Online portals preferred	No. of respondents	Percentage
1	Filpkart	32	24%
2	Amazon	78	60%
3	Jabong	-	-
4	Snapdeal	8	6%
5	Myntra	6	4%
6	Homeshop 18	2	2%
7	Shopclues	-	-
8	Bigbasket	2	2%
9	Smartshopper	-	-
10	Voonik	2	2%
11	Tech shop	-	-
Total		130	100

Source: Primary data

It is evident from table 3.7 that out of 130 respondents 24% of respondents are Purchasing via filpkart, 60% of respondents are purchasing via amazon, 6% of respondents are Purchasing via snapdeal, 4% of respondents are purchasing via mytra, 2% of respondents are Purchasing via Homeshop18, 2% of respondents are Purchasing via bigbasket, 2% of respondents are purchasing via voonik.

It is concluded that majority of the respondents (60%) are purchasing via amazon on online portal. Filp kart stands in their second priority (24%). The following figure 3.7 illuminates the same result.

Commodities / Service Preferred Through online shopping

S. No	Items	Yes	Percentage	No	Percentage
1	Accessories	64	(49%)	66	(51%)
2	Computer product	66	(51%)	64	(49%)
3	Clothing	84	(65%)	46	(35%)
4	Electronic gadgets	58	(45%)	72	(55%)
5	Books	50	(38%)	80	(62%)
6	Toys and gift	88	(68%)	42	(32%)
7	Bus / railway ticket	72	(55%)	58	(45%)
Total		130	100	130	100

Source: Primary data

It is evident from table that out of 130 respondents, 64(49%) respondents are purchasing Accessories through online shopping , 66(51%) respondents are not purchasing Accessories,

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66(51%) respondents are purchasing computer product through online shopping, 64(49%) respondents are not purchasing computer product, 84(65%) respondents are purchasing clothes through online shopping, 46 (35%) respondents are not purchasing clothes, 58(45%) respondents are purchasing electronic gadgets through online shopping, 72(55%) respondents are not purchasing electronic gadgets, 50(38%) respondents are purchasing books through online shopping, 80(62%) respondents are not purchasing books, 88(68%) respondents are purchasing toys and gifts through online shopping, 42(32%) respondents are not purchasing toys and gifts, 72(55%) respondents are booking Bus /railway ticket through online shopping, 58(45%) respondents are not booking Bus / railway ticket.

It is concluded that Majority of respondents are purchasing 88(68%) toys and gifts, through online shopping, Majority of respondents are not purchasing 80(62%) books. the result is not surprising because the college students prefer e-book. The following figure 3.8 Illuminate the same result.

Payment for Online Shopping

S. No	Payment for online shopping	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Debit card	24	18%
2	Credit card	50	66%
3	Cash on delivery	52	11%
4	Third Party(e. g, Pay pal, Pay tm, wallet).	4	3%
Total		130	100

Source: Primary data

It is evident from the table 3.12 that out of 130 respondents, 24(18%) respondents are using debit card for payment , 50(66%) respondents are using credit card of their parents for payment , 52(11%) respondents are preferred cash on delivery,4(3%) respondents are paid through to third Party (e.g, Pay tm)

It is concluded that the majority of the respondents are using credit card of their parents for online payment. The following figure 3.12 Illuminate the same result.

Rank the Advantage of Online Shopping

The Percentage score for each rank from 1 to 5 are calculated, the percentage score thus obtained for all the five ranks are converted in to scale values using scale conversion table given by Henry Garret. The scale values for first rank to five rank is 75,60,50,40, and 25 respectively.

Advantages for an Online Shopping

S. No.	Statement	I	II	III	IV	V	Total
1	Shop at any time of the day	78	40	8	2	2	130
2	The best window shopping without cost	22	72	24	6	6	130
3	Multiple payment gateway	34	22	42	24	8	130
4	Online shopping will eventually supersede traditional shopping	20	36	30	32	12	130
5	Social Network integration	28	40	34	18	10	130
6	Selection of goods available on the Internet is very broad	36	24	36	24	10	130
7	The description of product shown on the website varies	24	30	34	22	20	130
8	The information given about the product on the site	24	40	24	34	8	130
9	Creditability	34	30	32	22	12	130

10	Provision of home delivery	36	48	26	8	12	130
11	Privacy and secure checkout	26	30	38	26	10	130
12	Design /customer friendly	30	34	24	24	18	130

Findings of the Study

Findings based on the analysis and interpretations of the study are given below.

I Socio – economic profile of college student

- The majority (75%) of the respondent were female
- The majority (65%) of the respondent were between the age group (20-25).
- The majority (55%) of the respondents were Post graduate Students
- The Majority of the respondents' parent were earning Rs. 2,000 – Rs.5,000

II General Opinion on online shopping

- The all respondents were purchasing through online shopping
- The result revealed that the majority (51%) of the respondents were doing online shopping once in a week per month
- The Majority of the respondents (60%) were doing online shopping via amazon online portal
- The Majority of the respondents (68%) were purchased toys and gifts through online shopping
- The Majority of respondents (49%) used laptop for online shopping.
- The Majority of the respondents (89%) collected primary information before online shopping.
- The Majority of the respondents (60%) spent Rs.500 –Rs.1000 for online shopping.
- The Majority of the respondents (66%) paid via credit card for online shopping.
- The Majority of the respondents (66%) felt that online shopping save time.

Suggestions

- Majority of the respondents are collecting primary information before online shopping. Hence online retailers should focus on better home page presentation to appeal the potentials customers and sustain the existing customers.
- Goods quality should not deviate from the specification / image as shown in the online portal by e-trader.
- The consumers, government and online portal should simultaneously concentrate to secure online shopping.
- The online portal should secure their PC from viruses and other attacks by using a good anti-malware program.
- The e-stores specifically mention about the security of transactions of their e-stores which will increase the faith of customers for online shopping

Conclusion

Online shopping is becoming increasingly popular for a variety of reasons. The study brought to therefore that online shoppers are young, highly educated, active, intensive, and are expert users of the internet; they have a strong positive perception towards online shopping and generally spend a very low amount on online shopping. The findings of this research have confirmed that the perceived marketing mix and perceived reputation could impact on the college students' attitude of adopting online shopping. The largest driving factor for online shopping is the convenience. Through the findings of this research, online retailers could better realize online young customers' expectations and the determinants of young consumers' behavior. By understanding the attitude of college students towards online shopping, online retailers would be able to formulate and implement their e-business strategy efficiently and effectively and possess stronger competitive advantage.